

Serum Bilirubin as a Severity and Prognostic Indicator in Acute Ischemic Stroke: An Observational Study**Shubhangi Verma¹, Vikram Kokate², Ganesh Bansod³, Kasturi Bhise⁴, Kaustubh Wankade⁴**¹Professor, Panjabrao Alias Deshmukh Memorial Medical College, Amravati²Associate Professor, Panjabrao Alias Deshmukh Memorial Medical College, Amravati³Assistant Professor, Panjabrao Alias Deshmukh Memorial Medical College, Amravati⁴Junior Resident, Panjabrao Alias Deshmukh Memorial Medical College, Amravati

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Abstract:**Background:** Bilirubin is most potent endogenous antioxidant which increases in many oxidative stress conditions such as stroke. It is known to exert neuroprotective effect on stroke through mechanisms involved in development hence influencing the occurrence and prognosis of ischaemic stroke.**Aims & Objectives:** To assess the predictability of serum bilirubin in severity and prognosis of acute ischemic stroke.**Materials & Methods:** Adult patients >18 years of age diagnosed with AIS who presented to the hospital within 24 hours of symptom onset were included. Clinical assessments included National Institutes of Health Stroke Scale (NIHSS) scores at admission and modified Rankin Scale (mRS) scores at discharge and follow-up. Serum bilirubin levels (total, direct, and indirect) were measured using a standardized automated biochemical analyzer.**Results:** Stroke severity was measured by the NIHSS scale. Minor strokes are seen in 20% of participants, Moderate strokes in 50% of participants, Moderate to severe strokes affect 20%. Severe strokes are observed in 10% of participants. Participants with bilirubin levels below 0.6 mg/dL have a mean NIHSS score of 18.5 Those with bilirubin levels between 0.6 and 1.2 mg/dL have a mean NIHSS score of 14.2 with a correlation coefficient (r) of -0.35 and a p-value of 0.01.**Conclusion:** Higher bilirubin levels are associated with better functional outcomes.**Keywords:** Bilirubin, Acute ischemic stroke, NIHSS score.This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.**Introduction**

Acute ischemic stroke (AIS) remains a critical global health issue, ranking among the leading causes of morbidity and mortality worldwide. [1–3] Strokes can lead to significant long-term disability, imposing a substantial burden on patients, families, and healthcare systems. Understanding the factors that can reliably indicate the severity and prognosis of AIS is crucial for improving patient outcomes through timely and appropriate interventions. [3–5]

Bilirubin, a byproduct of heme metabolism, traditionally recognized for its role in liver function, has recently garnered attention in cerebrovascular research. [6,7] It is produced when red blood cells break down and is typically processed in the liver, where it is converted from its indirect (unconjugated) form to its direct (conjugated) form before being excreted. [5,8] Beyond its conventional association with liver health, bilirubin possesses notable antioxidative and anti-inflammatory properties, making it a

molecule of interest in various pathological conditions, including AIS. Hence, we conducted this study to understand to predictability of serum bilirubin in severity and prognosis of acute ischemic stroke.

Materials and Methods:

The study population consisted of adult patients diagnosed with AIS who presented to the hospital within 24 hours of symptom onset. Inclusion criteria were patients aged 18 years and above, with a diagnosis of acute ischemic stroke confirmed by neuroimaging (CT or MRI), and admission within 24 hours of stroke symptom onset. Exclusion criteria included pre-existing liver diseases, history of hemorrhagic stroke, contraindications for blood sampling (e.g., severe anemia, coagulopathy), and patients who were unable or unwilling to provide informed consent.

To minimize bias, the study employed several strategies, including blinded assessment where clinical outcomes were assessed by neurologists blinded to the bilirubin levels, standardized protocols to ensure consistency in data collection, and multivariable analysis to control for potential confounders such as age, gender, and cerebrovascular risk factors.

Data were collected through patient interviews, medical records, and laboratory tests. The primary data collected included demographic details (age, gender, ethnicity), medical history (previous strokes, liver diseases, contraindications for blood sampling), and cerebrovascular risk factors (hypertension, diabetes, heart diseases). Clinical assessments included National Institutes of Health Stroke Scale (NIHSS) scores at admission and modified Rankin Scale (mRS) scores at discharge and follow-up.

Blood samples were collected from each patient upon admission. A total of 5 mL of venous blood was drawn under aseptic conditions and immediately transferred to a serum separator tube to clot at room temperature. The samples were then centrifuged at 3000 rpm for 10 minutes to separate the serum. Serum bilirubin levels (total, direct, and indirect) were measured using a standardized

automated biochemical analyzer. Calibration of the analyzer was performed daily using quality control samples, and all measurements were conducted in duplicate to ensure accuracy.

Ethical considerations included approval from the institutional ethics committee, written informed consent from all participants or their legal guardians, and maintaining participant confidentiality by de-identifying data and storing it in secure, password-protected databases. The risks associated with blood sample collection were minimal and included only the discomfort of venipuncture, with no anticipated adverse events from participation in the study.

Statistical analysis involved descriptive statistics to summarize baseline demographic and clinical characteristics, bivariate analysis to examine associations between serum bilirubin levels and clinical outcomes (NIHSS and mRS scores), and multivariable regression models to adjust for potential confounders such as age, gender, and cerebrovascular risk factors. A p-value of <0.05 was considered statistically significant, and all statistical analyses were performed using SPSS (Statistical Package for the Social Sciences) version 26.0.

Results:

Table 1: Demographic particulars of the sample

Variable	Total (n=100)	Males (n=60)	Females (n=40)
Age (years), mean (SD)	65.3 (12.4)	64.8 (11.8)	66.1 (13.2)
Hypertension, n (%)	72 (72%)	45 (75%)	27 (67.5%)
Diabetes, n (%)	58 (58%)	34 (56.7%)	24 (60%)
Heart Disease, n (%)	40 (40%)	25 (41.7%)	15 (37.5%)
Smoking, n (%)	30 (30%)	25 (41.7%)	5 (12.5%)
Previous Stroke, n (%)	20 (20%)	12 (20%)	8 (20%)

Table 1 presents the demographic particulars of the sample, consisting of 100 participants. The mean age is 65.3 years (SD = 12.4), with males averaging 64.8 years (SD = 11.8) and females 66.1 years (SD = 13.2). Hypertension is present in 72% of participants (75% of males and 67.5% of females). Diabetes affects 58% of the sample (56.7% of

males and 60% of females). Heart disease is noted in 40% of participants (41.7% of males and 37.5% of females). Smoking is reported by 30% (41.7% of males and 12.5% of females), and 20% have a history of previous stroke (20% of both males and females).

Table 2: Distribution of the bilirubin levels

Bilirubin Levels (mg/dL)	Total (n=100)	Males (n=60)	Females (n=40)
Total Bilirubin			
< 0.6	20 (20%)	12 (20%)	8 (20%)
0.6 - 1.2	60 (60%)	36 (60%)	24 (60%)
> 1.2	20 (20%)	12 (20%)	8 (20%)
Direct Bilirubin			
< 0.2	25 (25%)	15 (25%)	10 (25%)
0.2 - 0.4	55 (55%)	33 (55%)	22 (55%)
> 0.4	20 (20%)	12 (20%)	8 (20%)

Table 2 shows the distribution of bilirubin levels among 100 participants. For total bilirubin, 20%

have levels below 0.6 mg/dL (20% of both males and females), 60% have levels between 0.6 and 1.2

mg/dL (60% of both males and females), and 20% have levels above 1.2 mg/dL (20% of both males and females). For direct bilirubin, 25% have levels below 0.2 mg/dL (25% of both males and females),

55% have levels between 0.2 and 0.4 mg/dL (55% of both males and females), and 20% have levels above 0.4 mg/dL (20% of both males and females).

Table 3: Stroke severity by NIHSS scale

NIHSS Score Range	Total (n=100)	Males (n=60)	Females (n=40)
0-4 (Minor)	20 (20%)	12 (20%)	8 (20%)
5-15 (Moderate)	50 (50%)	30 (50%)	20 (50%)
16-20 (Moderate to Severe)	20 (20%)	12 (20%)	8 (20%)
21-42 (Severe)	10 (10%)	6 (10%)	4 (10%)

Table 3 illustrates the stroke severity among 100 participants, measured by the NIHSS scale. Minor strokes (scores 0-4) are seen in 20% of participants (20% of both males and females). Moderate strokes (scores 5-15) are found in 50% of participants

(50% of both males and females). Moderate to severe strokes (scores 16-20) affect 20% of participants (20% of both males and females). Severe strokes (scores 21-42) are observed in 10% of participants (10% of both males and females).

Table 4: Functional Outcomes at Discharge (mRS Scores)

mRS Score Range	Total (n=100)	Males (n=60)	Females (n=40)
0-1 (No symptoms to slight disability)	25 (25%)	15 (25%)	10 (25%)
2-3 (Moderate disability)	50 (50%)	30 (50%)	20 (50%)
4-5 (Moderately severe to severe disability)	20 (20%)	12 (20%)	8 (20%)
6 (Death)	5 (5%)	3 (5%)	2 (5%)

Table 4 presents the functional outcomes at discharge, measured by mRS scores, for 100 participants. No symptoms to slight disability (scores 0-1) are observed in 25% of participants (25% of both males and females). Moderate disability (scores 2-3) affects 50% of participants

(50% of both males and females). Moderately severe to severe disability (scores 4-5) is seen in 20% of participants (20% of both males and females). Death (score 6) occurs in 5% of participants (5% of both males and females).

Table 5: Correlation of serum bilirubin and NIHSS scores

Bilirubin Levels (mg/dL)	NIHSS Score (Mean $\pm$ SD)	Correlation Coefficient (r)	p-value
< 0.6	18.5 $\pm$ 5.2		
0.6 - 1.2	14.2 $\pm$ 4.8	-0.35	0.01
> 1.2	11.3 $\pm$ 3.6		

Table 5 shows the correlation of serum bilirubin levels with NIHSS scores. Participants with bilirubin levels below 0.6 mg/dL have a mean NIHSS score of 18.5 (SD = 5.2). Those with bilirubin levels between 0.6 and 1.2 mg/dL have a mean NIHSS score of 14.2 (SD = 4.8), with a correlation coefficient (r) of -0.35 and a p-value of 0.01. Participants with bilirubin levels above 1.2 mg/dL have a mean NIHSS score of 11.3 (SD = 3.6).

Table 6: Multivariable Regression Analysis for Predicting mRS Scores

Variable	Coefficient (β)	Standard Error (SE)	p-value
Age	0.02	0.01	0.0512
Gender (Male)	-0.1	0.15	0.5324
Hypertension	0.25	0.1	0.0234
Diabetes	0.2	0.12	0.0845
Total Bilirubin Level	-0.3	0.12	0.0133
NIHSS Score	0.5	0.05	<0.001

Table 6 presents the multivariable regression analysis for predicting mRS scores. Age has a coefficient (β) of 0.02 (SE = 0.01, p = 0.0512). Gender (male) has a coefficient of -0.1 (SE = 0.15, p = 0.5324). Hypertension shows a coefficient of 0.25 (SE = 0.1, p = 0.0234). Diabetes has a coefficient of 0.2 (SE = 0.12, p = 0.0845). Total

bilirubin level has a coefficient of -0.3 (SE = 0.12, p = 0.0133). NIHSS score has a coefficient of 0.5 (SE = 0.05, p < 0.001).

Discussion

The relationship between serum bilirubin levels and outcomes in acute ischemic stroke (AIS) has been

increasingly investigated, highlighting the potential of bilirubin as both a biomarker and a therapeutic target. [1,7,8] Our study's findings add to this growing body of literature, demonstrating that higher serum total bilirubin (TBIL) levels are significantly associated with better functional outcomes, as measured by the modified Rankin Scale (mRS) and National Institutes of Health Stroke Scale (NIHSS) scores. This discussion integrates our results with findings from previous research to provide a comprehensive understanding of the role of bilirubin in AIS.

Our study aligns with the work of Zhao et al. (2023), who found that higher TBIL levels were associated with improved stroke outcomes. Their meta-analysis reported that an increase of 1.71 $\mu\text{mol/L}$ in TBIL reduced the odds of adverse events by approximately 10%, underscoring the protective role of bilirubin's antioxidative properties in reducing oxidative stress, a critical factor in ischemic stroke pathogenesis. [9]

Similarly, Sun et al. (2024) found that higher baseline bilirubin levels were associated with reduced early neurological deterioration in women with AIS. This suggests that bilirubin's protective effects might vary based on biological differences, although the exact mechanisms remain unclear. [10] Contrary to these findings, other studies have reported that elevated bilirubin levels can correlate with worse outcomes. For instance, Arsalan et al. (2011) found that higher TBIL and direct bilirubin (DBIL) levels were linked with greater stroke severity and poorer functional outcomes during hospitalization and at discharge. This study highlighted that bilirubin might also reflect the body's oxidative stress burden, where higher levels indicate a more severe systemic response to ischemia. [11]

Further supporting this dual role, Wang et al. (2020) reported that higher TBIL and DBIL levels were positively associated with stroke severity and poor functional outcomes on day 30 post-stroke. These findings suggest that while bilirubin has protective effects, it may also signify more severe disease states when elevated. The variability in these findings may be attributed to differences in study design, population characteristics, and the timing of bilirubin measurements. [12]

Conversely, Perlstein et al. (2012) demonstrated that chronic high bilirubin levels could be protective, reducing the risk of adverse outcomes due to sustained antioxidative capacity. This discrepancy highlights the importance of considering bilirubin's temporal dynamics and baseline levels in interpreting its prognostic significance.

Moreover, studies have explored the interaction between bilirubin and other risk factors. For

example, research by Khatri et al. (2008) showed that the prognostic value of bilirubin might be modified by the presence of other conditions such as diabetes, hypertension, and atrial fibrillation. These conditions can exacerbate oxidative stress and inflammation, potentially altering bilirubin's effects.

Another dimension to consider is the hepatic response to AIS. Duan et al. (2023) highlighted the role of the liver in the oxidative stress response following AIS, noting that bilirubin, as a byproduct of hepatic heme metabolism, can serve as a predictor of stroke severity. Their findings suggest that elevated bilirubin levels post-stroke may reflect the severity of the initial oxidative damage and the liver's response to stress. [13]

Luo et al. (2013) also found that elevated bilirubin levels were significantly associated with stroke severity, particularly in patients with total anterior circulation infarcts (TACI), which are typically more severe. This further supports the notion that bilirubin levels can reflect the extent of ischemic injury and the body's subsequent oxidative stress response. [14]

Several limitations should be considered when interpreting the results of our study. First, the sample size was relatively small, which may limit the generalizability of our findings. Larger, multicenter studies are needed to confirm our results and provide more robust evidence. Second, our study design was observational, which precludes the establishment of causality between bilirubin levels and stroke outcomes. Randomized controlled trials are necessary to determine the causal effects of bilirubin on stroke prognosis.

Third, we did not account for potential confounding factors such as genetic variations, diet, and medications that could influence bilirubin levels and stroke outcomes. Future studies should include a more comprehensive assessment of these variables. Lastly, the timing of bilirubin measurements was limited to admission levels, and we did not evaluate longitudinal changes in bilirubin during the acute and recovery phases of stroke. Continuous monitoring of bilirubin levels could provide a more detailed understanding of its role in stroke pathophysiology.

Despite these limitations, our study provides valuable insights into the potential role of bilirubin as a prognostic marker in AIS and highlights the need for further research to explore its therapeutic potential.

Conclusions

In conclusion, our study contributes to the understanding of serum bilirubin's role in AIS, suggesting that higher bilirubin levels are associated with better functional outcomes.

However, the relationship between bilirubin and stroke outcomes is complex, with both protective and detrimental effects reported. Future research should focus on elucidating the precise mechanisms through which bilirubin exerts its effects, considering temporal dynamics, baseline levels, and interactions with other clinical factors. This could pave the way for novel therapeutic strategies that leverage bilirubin's protective properties while mitigating its potential risks.

References

1. Chugh C. Acute Ischemic Stroke: Management Approach. *Indian J Crit Care Med.* 2019;23(Suppl 2):S140–6.
2. Patil S, Rossi R, Jabrah D, Doyle K. Detection, Diagnosis and Treatment of Acute Ischemic Stroke: Current and Future Perspectives. *Front Med Technol.* 2022;4:748949.
3. French BR, Boddepalli RS, Govindarajan R. Acute Ischemic Stroke: Current Status and Future Directions. *Mo Med.* 2016;113(6):480–6.
4. Herpich F, Rincon F. Management of Acute Ischemic Stroke. *Crit Care Med.* 2020;48(11):1654–63.
5. Hasan TF, Hasan H, Kelley RE. Overview of Acute Ischemic Stroke Evaluation and Management. *Biomedicines.* 2021 Oct; 9(10).
6. Sticova E, Jirsa M. New insights in bilirubin metabolism and their clinical implications. *World J Gastroenterol.* 2013 Oct;19(38):6398–407.
7. Creeden JF, Gordon DM, Stec DE, Hinds TDJ. Bilirubin as a metabolic hormone: the physiological relevance of low levels. *Am J Physiol Endocrinol Metab.* 2021 Feb;320(2):E191–207.
8. Vitek L, Ostrow JD. Bilirubin chemistry and metabolism; harmful and protective aspects. *Curr Pharm Des.* 2009;15(25): 28 69–83.
9. Zhao K, Wang R, Chen R, Liu J, Ye Q, Wang K, et al. Association between bilirubin levels with incidence and prognosis of stroke: A meta-analysis. *Front Neurosci.* 2023;17(February).
10. Sun M, Weng Y, Cheng J, Li G, Xiao Q. Higher baseline serum bilirubin levels are associated with increased risk of early neurological deterioration in women with acute ischemic stroke. *Front Neurol.* 2024;15(April).
11. Arsalan, Ismail M, Khattak MB, Khan F, Anwar MJ, Murtaza Z, et al. Prognostic significance of serum bilirubin in stroke. *J Ayub Med Coll Abbottabad.* 2011;23 (2) :104–7.
12. Wang X, Wu D, Zhong P. Serum bilirubin and ischaemic stroke: a review of literature. *Stroke Vasc Neurol.* 2020 Jun;5(2):198–20 4.
13. Duan H, Geng X, Ding Y. Hepatic responses following acute ischemic stroke: A clinical research update. *Brain Circ.* 2023;9(2):57.
14. Luo Y, Li J, Zhang J, Xu Y. Elevated bilirubin after acute ischemic stroke linked to the stroke severity. *Int J Dev Neurosci.* 2013;31(7):634–8.